

Design and utilization of a decision support tool to advance energy efficiency in industries

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ABSTRACT

The industrial sector contributes significant environmental impact due to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. It is necessary to investigate the energy flow from resources, and the possibilities for lowering energy use through energy management. Energy modeling and visualization have been identified as effective and powerful methods for investigating energy-saving potential and improving energy efficiency. In this study, the Sankey diagram-based decision support tool is designed and developed to illustrate the energy flow and the potential for energy savings from various processes in different industrial sectors. The tool is developed in Python and presented as a web-based dashboard, making it accessible to various users. The web-based Sankey diagram tool allows the user to comprehend the present state of energy consumption, costs, and CO₂ emissions, as well as the potential for enhancing system flexibility and efficiency in the industry. The opportunities for heat recovery, renewable energy sources, and energy storage technologies are discussed as an assumed case study in 4 specific scenarios. Finally, the findings validate the significance of energy-efficient solutions in industry utilizing the proposed tool. This underscores the importance of adopting sustainable practices within industries, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of the sector's overall sustainability and resilience.

1. Introduction

The industrial sector, contributing 29 % of total CO₂ emissions, plays a significant role in global warming [1]. Both the utilization of fossil fuels and high-temperature industrial processes frequently result in such emissions. Reducing industrial CO₂ emissions is essential for a variety of reasons. First, lowering the atmospheric emissions of greenhouse gases directly slows down climate change [2]. Second, high carbon emissions can result in increased operational costs for industries due to regulatory compliance, carbon pricing, and the potential for reputational damage [3]. Industries can improve their long-term economic resilience and competitiveness by using cleaner and more sustainable processes [4].

The energy sector, accounting for 80 percent of total carbon emissions, has the greatest influence [5]. Several industrial sectors are notably carbon-intensive due to their reliance on energy-intensive processes and fossil fuels [6]. The iron and steel industry, for instance, are massive contributors to CO₂ emissions because of the use of blast furnaces and basic oxygen furnaces [7]. Similarly, another major contributor due to the calcination process and the amount of fuel combustion used in the industry is the cement industry [8]. Chemical industry

subsectors within the fertilizer and plastic branches encompass energy-intensive processes like steam cracking and ammonia synthesis [9]. Energy-intensive petroleum refining emits large volumes of CO₂ and methane. Large mitigation measures in these critical sectors encompass improvements in energy use, cleaner technologies, increased use of renewable energy, and broader use of carbon capture and storage technologies [10].

Energy storage systems that integrate renewable energy (RE) sources are gaining popularity in manufacturing and other industrial sectors [11,12]. Renewable energy plays an important role in industry by reducing its environmental impact through significantly lowering harmful emissions [13,14]. Its cost-effectiveness lowers operational expenses, enhancing the economic viability of industrial processes [15]. In addition, the reliability of renewable energies such as solar and wind ensures a constant energy supply and minimizes disturbances [16]. Energy storage is paramount in industries, as it optimizes energy use, enhances grid stability, and mitigates power interruptions [17]. It enables industries to efficiently manage fluctuating energy demands, lowering operational costs and reliance on grid power during peak periods [18]. Energy storage solutions, such as batteries and hydrogen

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storage, contribute to grid resilience and provide backup power [19], which is crucial for uninterrupted production processes. Furthermore, they support the adoption of RE sources in order to ensure a sustainable and dependable energy supply for industrial activities [20].

Industries utilize heat recovery as well as thermal storages to enhance energy efficiency by capturing and reusing waste heat from operations, hence reducing energy consumption and operating costs. This approach also diminishes the environmental impact by decreasing greenhouse gas emissions [21]. It enhances industrial competitiveness by conserving energy resources and can even generate additional revenue through the sale of recovered heat or improved process efficiency [22]. Furthermore, heat recovery aligns with sustainability goals, making industries more environmentally responsible and economically viable [23]. Fig. 1 shows the energy flow of main components in industrial sectors considering renewable energies, energy storage, as well as heat recovery potential.

Advanced technology plays a pivotal role in industries throughout the Fourth Industrial Revolution by fostering innovation, enhancing productivity, and boosting competitiveness [24]. Systems powered by automation and artificial intelligence enhance operational efficiency by reducing the occurrence of human mistakes [25]. In addition, these technologies facilitate resource management and cost savings through data-driven decision-making [26]. Furthermore, sophisticated technology contributes to sustainability by lowering energy usage and environmental effects [27]. The importance of sophisticated technology, particularly in decision support tools, has emerged as a critical component in the transformation of modern industries, with a particular emphasis on energy engineering and RE. These industries have witnessed a profound shift driven by the fusion of innovation and data-driven decision-making [28]. These tools serve as a bridge between traditional industry practices and the dynamic demands of our rapidly evolving world [29].

Visualization of energy flow has caught the interest of professionals and academics in the domains of energy engineering and RE [30–33]. The idea of real-time adaptation in energy management is captured perfectly by this dynamic concept. This adaptability leads to heightened efficiency, cost savings, and a profound reduction in environmental impact. Effective communication of complex data and concepts within these industries often relies on the utilization of visual aids [34]. Among these, Sankey diagrams stand out as a powerful tool [35–37]. These graphics demonstrate the complicated movement and transformation of energy and resources within industrial processes [38]. With its straightforward style, Sankey diagrams provide stakeholders with a clear window into the dynamics of energy flow, promoting a deeper understanding of operations and identifying areas for optimization [39–41].

The use of energy visualization technologies to improve energy usage has been the subject of some research in recent years, but there is still room for more evaluation, particularly in the areas of industrial energy

management. In Ref. [42] the complex web-based platform is designed to remotely monitor the energy consumption and the number of machined parts, allowing remote control over manufacturing processes. In Ref. [43] an Enimo-energy dashboard was designed to connect to the sensors and visualize energy electricity consumption of industrial cases. The authors of [44] created a tool that measures process resource efficiency and visually traces the use of both energy and materials from available control data using a Sankey diagram. However, data-uploading processes are typically complex, and visualization necessarily requires significant adaptation and engineering knowledge. Furthermore, the research did not focus on how to optimize energy use by using emerging technology. Moreover, the potential for enhancing industrial sustainability is overestimated because the research does not take into account the adaptability of adding new features. In addition, the user had to pay more to have access to non-open-source software.

The research in this paper designed and developed a novel Sankey diagram-based decision support tool (SanFlex-DST) to illustrate energy flow and potential energy savings from different industrial processes. The tool's Python codebase and web-based interface make it accessible to a wide range of users. There are several research being conducted on the concept of decarbonization and energy cost reduction in industry. However, the results are complex and rarely applicable to other case studies. One of the key goals of this research is to provide a general, easy, and effective tool that engineers and non-engineers, such as project managers and accountants, can utilize through a web page. The primary objective of this project is to create and implement an open-source solution for assisting with decision-making in industrial energy management systems. The program's visualization of the energy stream can help its users gain a deeper comprehension of the role that each component plays in terms of energy consumption, efficiency, and savings. Streamlining energy management also improves resilience and contributes to regulatory compliance, which is consistent with sustainability objectives. Users can also quickly add or remove components such as renewable energy, energy storage technologies as well as heat recovery solutions to test the system's feasibility and evaluate future opportunities to improve a sector's sustainability. The tool also has the benefit of being able to calculate energy costs and carbon emissions in order to assess the current state of the sector and determine whether new, efficient technologies can be used. The results and findings of the current study can then be used by practitioners in the industrial sector to make accurate decisions that will improve efficiency and contribute to the sector's long-term viability.

As a result, section 2 of this paper will address the overview of system design and the architecture of the proposed web-based tool. In section 3, the results of the tool's application and strategy will be discussed with the help of a case study. In section 4, a discussion of various integration scenarios will be conducted in order to determine the viability of integrating new efficient technologies and waste heat recovery utilizing SANFLEX-DST tool. Additionally, carbon footprint and cost analyses will be conducted for all four scenarios. The conclusion will then be presented in section 5.

2. System design and structure

The integration of advanced technology, energy streaming, and visual aids like Sankey diagrams offers a myriad of benefits to industries. These tools provide a sound, data-driven foundation upon which businesses can construct informed decisions, optimize resource allocation, and navigate the multifaceted terrain of risk. In addition, they enable industries to ensure strict compliance with ever-changing regulations and reporting requirements, thereby minimizing the risk of expensive noncompliance. In this section, the fundamental design of the proposed tool and its position within the energy system are discussed.

Fig. 1. Energy flow and heat recovery in industries.

2.1. Incorporation of SanFlex-DST

Energy management and monitoring can help a company cut costs by reducing usage and consumption as well as by reducing its reliance on occasionally unstable supply chains. Programs for energy management can assist businesses with cost reduction through competitive procurement. In order to help users make better decisions, the suggested SanFlex-DST visualization tool can be installed and integrated into an energy management system. Fig. 2 shows the proposed integration of SanFlex-DST as a part of industrial energy management systems.

2.2. Architecture of the web-based tool

Accessibility and user-friendliness are the primary goals of the developed tool. Thus, the tool was built and developed in a visual studio software [45] as a web-based environment, and users may quickly access the main dashboard and design their own case studies by accessing the link. The dash library [46] as one of the best and most advanced dashboards for Python, is utilized for the visualization of Sankey diagrams and energy flow. Also, there are some additional libraries, such as Pandas [47] and Plotly [48]. The most important functions in the design and development of the tool are importing libraries, initial visualization for user reference, building tables for directly adding values, callbacks, and finally, results and visualization. Fig. 3 briefly explains the process of design and development of the proposed tool.

Following the importation of the libraries and the definition of the initial Sankey diagrams for baseline and modified energy flows, the total cost and CO₂ emission will be evaluated based on the initial inputs of the table. Users have the ability to simply modify the values included within the table of constant parameters and the table of values. Additionally, by clicking on the update button, the graph will be changed. Furthermore, in order to determine the adaptability of the system, a variety of sliders and functions have been introduced in order to update the changed energy flow graph in accordance with the scenarios that the user requires.

2.3. Table of constant parameters

Having a general tool to cover gas, electricity, renewable energies, energy storage systems, cost, and CO₂ emission estimations requires basic value considerations that can be easily changed based on project specifications. As a result, the table of constant parameters that is shown in Table 1. is established to include all the constant values.

In accordance with each case study, the user is able to quickly and easily modify the effectiveness of parameters and update cost and CO₂ emission-related values. Immediately following any modification to a value in the table, that modification will be reflected in the list of

Fig. 3. SanFlex-DST design process stages.

Table 1
Constant parameters.

Parameters	Units
Maximum possible RE Generation	kWh
H2 Storage Efficiency	%
Battery Storage Efficiency	%
Thermal energy storage efficiency	%
CO ₂ emission of Gas	gCO ₂ /kWh
CO ₂ emission of Electricity	gCO ₂ /kWh
Electricity cost	€/kWh
Gas cost	€/kWh

constant parameter variables. With respect to the table’s maximum RE generation capacity, users can promptly determine the system’s flexibility constraints and maximum generating potential by calculating the maximum quantity of RE that can be produced. Fig. 4 explains the process of updating the table of constant parameters in the tool.

2.4. Data visualization of energy flow

Energy is the backbone of the industrial sector, providing the fuel that keeps machines and operations running. Certified Energy Management Systems (EnMS), particularly those accredited to ISO 50001, emphasize the paramount significance of initially identifying the precise destinations of energy consumption. This initial step serves as the cornerstone for effective energy management. By understanding where energy is being utilized within an organization, it becomes possible to pinpoint inefficiencies, optimize processes, and implement targeted energy-saving measures. Energy flow visualizations as a part of an energy management system can help with the analysis and optimization of a system’s performance by showing how energy is distributed and transformed within the system. The process of accessing data, uploading that data, and visualizing the results typically takes a significant amount of time and is complicated. As a result, the developed tool allows the user to enter data directly into the tables and update the graphs by

Fig. 2. SanFlex-DST as a part of the energy management system.

Fig. 4. The process of updating table of constant parameters.

clicking on the update button. As an example, Table 2. shows the mechanism of the table of values in the tool. By running the tool based on the values inside the table, the Sankey diagram will be shown in Fig. 5.

The table should comprehensively list energy sources and their corresponding consumers, detailing precise energy flows at each node, aligning with Sankey diagram requirements. This structured dataset, essential for energy analysis, enables a visual representation of energy distribution, aiding in optimizing industrial processes and advancing energy engineering practices. Fig. 6 shows the process of adding and

Table 2
Table of values.

Energy Source	Consumer	Values (kWh)
Source 1	Consumer 1	40
Source 2	Consumer 1	20
Source 2	Consumer 3	50
Source 2	Consumer 4	30
Source 3	Consumer 3	20
Source 3	Consumer 2	60

Fig. 5. Simple visualization for the table of values in Sankey diagram.

Fig. 6. Process of updating table of values.

updating values in the table of values.

2.5. Cost and CO₂ emission evaluations

The decrease in CO₂ emissions and costs is one of the most important factors that might lead to an increase in the industry's level of sustainability. With the help of the tool, users easily can estimate the CO₂ emissions and costs based on energy use for baseline and modified

energy graphs. Additionally, the solution for reducing CO₂ emissions and lowering costs will be illustrated in terms of the utilization of renewable energies, energy storage, and heat recovery solutions.

Considering electricity and gas as two main types of energy use for electrical and thermal equipment in industrial sectors, Eq. (1) explains the tool's background cost calculation related to the total electricity consumption in the industry:

$$Cost_{elec(total)} = \sum_{i=1}^n (E_{elec(total)} \times Cost_{elec}) \quad (1)$$

where $E_{elec(total)}$ represents the total energy use of electricity and $Cost_{elec}$ denotes the cost factor of electricity use based on €/kWh. Eq. (2) explains total fuel consumption costs considering heat recovery factor as one of the solutions of reducing fuel energy consumption:

$$Cost_{fuel(total)} = \sum_{i=1}^n ([E_{fuel(total)} - E_{hr(total)}] \times Cost_{fuel}) \quad (2)$$

where $E_{fuel(total)}$ represents the total energy use of fuel, $E_{hr(total)}$ corresponds to total possible heat that can be collected and reused to reduce fuel consumption, and $Cost_{fuel}$ denotes the cost factor of fuel energy use based on €/kWh.

Total energy cost as sum of energy costs of fuel and electricity can be explained in Eq. (3) as follows:

$$Cost_{total} = Cost_{elec(total)} + Cost_{fuel(total)} \quad (3)$$

in terms of checking carbon footprint in industrial sectors and demonstrating the potential to reduce, Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) show the total CO₂ emissions related to electricity and gas consumptions and finally, Eq. (6) explains total CO₂ emissions in industry as the sum of Eq. (4) and Eq. (5):

$$CO_{2elec(total)} = \sum_{i=1}^n (E_{elec(total)} \times e_{elec}) \quad (4)$$

and

$$CO_{2fuel(total)} = \sum_{i=1}^n ([E_{fuel(total)} - E_{hr(total)}] \times e_{fuel}) \quad (5)$$

then:

$$CO_{2total} = CO_{2elec(total)} + CO_{2fuel(total)} \quad (6)$$

where e_{elec} and e_{fuel} signify the emission factor of energy consumption for gas and electricity based on the g CO₂/kWh.

2.6. Accessing the SanFlex tool

The primary goal of this tool is to ensure seamless accessibility through the internet. Thus, a fundamental objective is its development as a user-friendly web-based utility. By simplifying its design and architecture, the tool is intended to be easily navigable and intuitive. This approach underscores a commitment to user convenience, allowing swift and straightforward access to the tool's functionalities, promoting efficiency, and enhancing the overall user experience.

Fig. 7 shows the primary dashboard that works based on fundamental introductory information to deliver an initial visualization for user references. The significance of this tool is to illustrate the current circumstance and potential of adaptability and system enhancement in industries. The pattern outlines the current situation of the system and the amount of energy streams from sources to different consumers. Within the modified graph, there are different extra components such as RE, two sorts of energy storages as well as a thermal storage to collect from each step and store for later. There are particular sliders for each component that the user can easily manipulate to check the cost and CO₂ emission based on the current situation or alternative modified energy flows that illustrate the significance of adaptability and system improvement. Also, the user can update the graphs and add data directly into the tables and by clicking on the update button.

3. Results

To demonstrate the resilience of the methodology and system design,

Fig. 7. The initial dashboard of SanFlex tool.

a series of test cases are devised inside a hypothetical industry case study. These test cases encompass several integrations, including RE, battery, and hydrogen energy storage. The purpose of these test cases is to assess the capabilities of the SanFlex-DST. In the following section, a more in-depth discussion of the system design of the tool is presented by outlining a number of different scenarios and providing illustrations of potential implementations of the approach as a proof of concept.

Fig. 8 shows the simple energy flow diagram of an assumed industrial case. The presented diagram illustrates the integration of renewable and traditional energy sources in an industrial energy flow system, together with the use of multiple storage methods. The visualization features three main energy sources: a renewable energy source, electricity from the grid, and natural gas. The RE, possibly solar panels, produces electricity power instantly. Electricity is also supplied to the system from the external grid. Conversely, natural gas is combusted in a specialised component, such as a boiler, to generate thermal energy. The diagram illustrates the use of a thermal main hub and an electrical main hub to efficiently distribute the generated energy. All industrial components, are connected to these hubs to fulfil their energy requirements. Furthermore, any extra energy usage associated with measurement instruments, linear motors, etc. is categorised as “other”. This system’s significant feature is the incorporation of energy storage methods. Batteries and hydrogen storage devices capture electrical energy for later electrical and thermal use respectively, improving grid stability and system flexibility. Waste heat generated from possible processes is gathered via appropriate technologies such as heat exchangers and then directed to a central heat collector. The reclaimed heat can be redirected back to the central thermal system for possible reuse, enhancing the energy efficiency of the system. The technique focuses on using a variety of approaches, combining renewable energy sources with traditional methods, emphasising heat recovery in a thermal storage, and utilizing various storage technologies to enhance sustainability and economic feasibility.

3.1. Updating the table of constant parameters

After accessing the tool, the first thing that needs to be done is to change the table of constant parameters. The constant parameters are detailed in Table 3. These constant parameters were supposed to be the same throughout this research project regardless of the scenarios. It is essential to be aware that the efficiency criteria are inextricably linked to the types of machines in industrial settings. When it comes to energy storage, batteries are supposed to have an efficiency of 85 %, which indicates that the value at which the battery is discharged consists of 85 % of the entire value that was input [49]. The same aspects can happen with hydrogen energy, which implies that its efficiency can be deemed to be at a level of 50 % [50]. This, in turn, indicates that the maximum total discharge value for hydrogen energy can be no higher than fifty

Fig. 8. Energy flow diagram in an industrial case study.

Table 3
Updated constant parameters.

Parameters	Value
Maximum possible RE Generation (GWh)	400
H2 Storage Efficiency (%)	50
Battery Storage Efficiency (%)	85
Efficiency of Recoverable Heat (%)	80
CO ₂ emission of Gas (kgCO ₂ /MWh)	0.202
CO ₂ emission of Electricity (kgCO ₂ /MWh)	0.331
Electricity cost (£/kWh)	0.38
Gas cost (£/kWh)	0.11

percent of its maximum total input value. In terms of heat recovery, thermal storage efficiency is considered 80 %, which means the total efficiency of heat collection from possible processes, where heat recovery is an option, and storing them in thermal storage for reuse is considered 80 %. The cost and the related values for the carbon footprint, available collected heat, etc. are totally tied to the particular location and industries in which the components are installed. The values that were considered for each of them are listed in the table that can be found below.

3.2. Updating the table of values

The main components of the system for this study consist of RE sources, electricity, and gas as the three main sources of energy that are usually consumed in industrial sectors, the connected components to the system, and their heat recovery components. The process of updating the table of values involves a straightforward task of modifying and adjusting the data and labels within the table. This table serves as a convenient tool for managing the components of the system. It includes essential elements such as RE sources, electricity, and gas as the primary energy sources prevalent in industrial sectors. Additionally, it outlines the interconnected components within the system, along with their corresponding heat recovery potentials. Therefore, the table of values is proposed, as shown in Table 4. The consumption values in this case study have been approximated based on a combination of actual 1-year data and assumptions around individual process run times. The apparent simplicity of this table may mislead an individual into believing that the process of revising and updating information is quite simple. Although the system’s structure may be intuitive at first glance, the task of ensuring data accuracy and consistency poses a deeper and more complicated challenge. Acquiring the data that comprises this table necessitates an in-depth knowledge of the field and the particular metrics being recorded.

3.3. Updating baseline energy flow

Once clicking on the update button, the baseline graph will display the value as well as the name of each energy flow link. This will take place after the names of each node and their values have been updated.

As it is clear in Fig. 9, each node and its connection represent the values of the table. When utilizing Sankey diagrams, one of the advantages is that the level of intensity of energy consumption that is connected to each component can be represented with the assistance of this tool. Users are able to gain a deeper comprehension of the operation of the system and examine the various possibilities for improving energy efficiency as a result of this. It is essential to keep in mind that the nodes labeled “thermal” and “electricity” respectively stand in for the required amounts of energy to satisfy both thermal and electrical consumption. Additionally, the heat recovery potential for just those possible components that have the capability of collecting heat and are connected to the heat recovery system can be displayed in the graph. That is, thermal storage simply collects the feasible heat from operations that generate enough thermal energy to be collected and stored in thermal storage for future use.

Table 4
Editable table of values.

Energy Source	Consumer	Value (GWh/year)
E-Grid	Electricity	811.816
REs	Electricity	87.6
Gas	Thermal	586.612
REs	Battery Storage	131.4
REs	H2 Storage	131.4
Battery Storage	Electricity	131.4
H2 Storage	Thermal	131.4
Electricity	Electric Furnace 1	305.4
Electricity	Electric Furnace 2	305.4
Electricity	Laddle Furnace 1	31.1
Electricity	Laddle Furnace 2	31.1
Electricity	Tundish	8.5
Electricity	Continues Casting	15
Electricity	Reheating Furnace	0
Electricity	Rolling Mill 1	51.5
Electricity	Rolling Mill 2	34.1
Electricity	Rolling Mill 3	17
Electricity	Other	13
Thermal	Electric Furnace 1	0
Thermal	Electric Furnace 2	0
Thermal	Laddle Furnace 1	0
Thermal	Laddle Furnace 2	0
Thermal	Tundish	0
Thermal	Continues Casting	0
Thermal	Reheating Furnace	570
Thermal	Rolling Mill 1	0
Thermal	Rolling Mill 2	0
Thermal	Rolling Mill 3	0
Thermal	Other	16.612
Electric Furnace 1	Thermal Storage	50
Electric Furnace 2	Thermal Storage	50
Laddle Furnace 1	Thermal Storage	10
Laddle Furnace 2	Thermal Storage	10
Tundish	Thermal Storage	5
Continues Casting	Thermal Storage	0
Reheating Furnace	Thermal Storage	100
Rolling Mill 1	Thermal Storage	0
Rolling Mill 2	Thermal Storage	0
Rolling Mill 3	Thermal Storage	0

Fig. 9. Baseline energy flow.

3.4. Scenarios description

This tool aims to evaluate the viability of integrating various forms of RE, as well as energy storage and heat recovery. In this way, four scenarios inside the assumed industrial case have been built in order to test various combinations of RE sources, energy storage devices, and thermal

energy storage. These scenarios have been crafted in order to evaluate these diverse combinations. Additionally, the tool has a central panel that incorporates a renewable generation integrator, in addition to four specific sliders that enable the user to simply modify the quantity of each component based on the values that have been input into the table of values. Apart from the thermal storage slider, the main panel features three additional sliders illustrating various scenarios of renewable integration. These scenarios range from directly decreasing electricity and gas usage to charging energy storage systems.

a) Before implementations (Base Case)

In the first possible scenario, considering the position of sliders, the system consists of its fundamental components but lacks effective integration solutions. As shown in Fig. 10, there are primarily two categories of energy sources: gas and electricity. Additionally, there is no thermal storage component included in the system. It indicates that there are no alternatives for heat recovery or heat collection. The positions of the sliders indicate that there is no integration of renewable energy for either charging energy storage devices or directly lowering the amount of power that is consumed. In the first scenario, the key flexibility indicator is a representation of the integration of renewable energies, which is zero.

Total CO₂ emission and total cost regarding the current situation of the system can be calculated as below:

$$CO_{2s_1} = (e_{elec} \times E_{elec(total)} + (e_{fuel} \times E_{fuel(total)})) = 387.2 \text{ t CO}_2 / \text{year}$$

and

$$Cost_{s_1} = (Cost_{elec} \times E_{elec(total)} + (Cost_{fuel} \times E_{fuel(total)})) = \text{€}373 \text{ million} \setminus / \text{year}$$

b) Renewable Energy and Thermal Storage Integrations

Scenario 2 as shown in Fig. 11, the system incorporates RE and a thermal storage mechanism but lacks energy storage integration solutions. In this situation, the renewable generation indicator displays the RE consumption that is solely used to reduce electricity usage. The sliders are set to 0 for energy storage and to the maximum for heat recovery and RE utilization sliders. The energy transfer from RE sources to electricity follows the input value inside the table of values. It is important to highlight that there is still a connection between RE, energy storage, electricity, and thermal nodes, just for illustration, and there is no energy flow in the specified connections.

Fig. 10. Scenario 1: System's current situation.

Fig. 11. Scenario 2: Renewable energy and thermal storage integrations.

Total CO₂ emission and total cost considering the direct integration of renewable energy for electricity consumption reduction can be evaluated as below:

$$CO_{2s2} = (e_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - E_{RES}) + (e_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - E_{HR}))) = 329.9 \text{ t CO}_2 / \text{year}$$

and

$$Cost_{s2} = (Cost_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - E_{RES})) + (Cost_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - E_{HR})) = \text{€}324.3 \text{ million / year}$$

c) Energy Storages and Heat Recovery Integrations

In scenario 3, the option of utilizing RE to directly reduce electricity consumption from the grid is excluded from the evaluation. In this specific scenario that is illustrated in Fig. 12, where there is no direct energy flow from renewable sources for reducing electricity consumption, the value of 263 GWh signifies the combined energy used per year for hydrogen storage and battery charging.

The positioning of the RE slider is the basis for this decision-making. Taking into consideration the efficiency parameter that is contained in the table of constant parameters for batteries, battery storage is

Fig. 12. Scenario 3: Energy storage and heat recovery integrations.

responsible for a reduction in the amount of electricity that is consumed in relation to charging values acquired from a renewable energy source. In addition, hydrogen energy achieves the same objective by obtaining power from renewable sources and releasing the same amount of power while taking into consideration the efficiency factor when doing so. As a measure of renewable flexibility integration, the total amount of renewable energy that is used for hydrogen and energy storage charging is displayed.

Considering the integration of battery storage and hydrogen energy storage, the total CO₂ emission and total cost can be achieved as below:

$$CO_{2s3} = (e_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - E_{BESS})) + (e_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - (E_{H2} + E_{HR}))) = 308.7 \text{ t CO}_2 / \text{year}$$

and

$$Cost_{s3} = (Cost_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - E_{BESS})) + (Cost_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - (E_{H2} + E_{HR}))) = \text{€}307.9 \text{ million / year}$$

d) Renewable Energy, Energy Storage and Heat recovery Integrations

Lastly, in scenario 4, the system incorporates a solution for heat recovery in addition to RE, energy storage in the form of batteries and hydrogen energy storage. Regarding Fig. 13, the indication in this scenario displays the maximum amount of feasible energy flow from renewable sources to each of the connected components. The sliders are assumed to be set to their highest possible levels to display the system's full capability for efficiently integrating new components. RE is not only helping to charge energy storages, but it is also compensating for the amount of electricity that is being consumed from the grid depending on the numbers that are entered into the table. RE-connected battery technology is also helping to cut down on the amount of grid electricity used, while RE-connected hydrogen energy storage is helping to cut down on the amount of imported gas used. This indicates that the system is thought to be operating at its most efficient level, which allows for further improvements in the system's efficiency. Therefore, the graph illustrates the reduction in the primary sources of energy that will result in a lower overall CO₂ emission level and a lower overall cost associated with energy consumption.

Total CO₂ emission and total cost integrating full potential of efficient technologies can be calculated as below:

Fig. 13. Scenario 4: Renewable energy, energy storage and heat recovery integrations.

$$CO_{2s4} = (e_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - (E_{RES} + E_{BESS}))) + (e_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - (E_{HR} + E_{H2}))) = 279.7 \text{ t CO}_2 / \text{year}$$

and

$$Cost_{s4} = (Cost_{elec} \times (E_{elec(total)} - (E_{RES} + E_{BESS}))) + (Cost_{fuel} \times (E_{fuel(total)} - (E_{HR} + E_{H2}))) = \text{€}274.7 \text{ million / year}$$

4. Discussion

In the Base Case scenario, the system runs on its core components without any sophisticated integration solutions. As illustrated in Fig. 10, the primary energy sources are gas and electricity, with no thermal storage or renewable energy integration. Consequently, the flexibility indicator for renewable energy is 0. This results in total CO₂ emissions of 387.2 tons per year and annual expenses of €373 million, indicating considerable environmental and economic impacts.

In Scenario 2, the system combines RE with thermal storage, as shown in Fig. 11. Despite the lack of energy storage technologies, renewable energy is employed to reduce electricity usage while maximizing heat recovery and RE utilization. This integration reduces CO₂ emissions at 329.9 tons per year and costs €324.3 million per year, highlighting the benefits of partial sustainable integration.

Scenario 3 incorporates a battery energy storage system with hydrogen storage, as seen in Fig. 12. Annually, 263 GWh of energy is allocated for storage, lowering CO₂ emissions to 308.7 tons per year and costs to €307.9 million. This emphasizes the role of energy storage in increasing system flexibility while lowering emissions and costs.

Finally, scenario 4 shown in Fig. 13, includes RE, energy storage (battery and hydrogen), and heat recovery, indicating the system’s full integration potential. RE charges storage systems and reduces grid power usage, resulting in the lowest CO₂ emissions of 279.7 tons per year and annual costs of €274.7 million. This scenario demonstrates the significant environmental and economic advantages of a fully integrated, efficient energy management system.

Table 5. is designed to compare the energy cost and the amount of CO₂ emission based on 4 scenarios. Also, Figs. 14 and 15 designed to illustrate the trends of total cost and total carbon foot-print based on each scenarios. The result demonstrates cost savings and decrease in the carbon footprint, which is achieved by incorporating more energy-efficient equipment. The result of scenario 1 demonstrates the fundamental use of energy without any efficient solutions, but the result of scenario 4, which is the most advanced scenario among all of them, shows a decrease in CO₂ and total energy related cost.

All results were achieved with the help of the proposed SANFLEX tool, illustrating the importance and advancement of the tool for utilizing different efficient components in industries. This tool enables the visualization and integration of various technologies, allowing for the comprehensive analysis of energy costs and carbon emissions. By employing SANFLEX, users and decision-makers can gain a deeper understanding of the current energy system and identify opportunities for enhancing energy efficiency within industrial settings.

Table 5
Table of cost and carbon footprint.

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
Renewable Energy	×	✓	×	✓
Energy Storage	×	×	✓	✓
Recoverable Heat	×	✓	✓	✓
Energy Cost (€ million/year)	373	324.3	307.9	274.7
Total CO ₂ (t CO ₂ / year)	387.2	329.9	308.7	279.7

Fig. 14. Total CO₂ emission comparison.

Fig. 15. Total cost comparison.

5. Conclusion

This research developed a web-based tool called SanFlex-DST to support energy management in industrial sectors. The tool uses Sankey diagram visualization to show current energy flow and potential benefits of renewable energy sources and energy storage technologies. It also explores heat recovery collection in thermal energy storage systems to reduce fossil fuel use. The tool’s effectiveness was assessed using four scenarios from a case study. Finally, this study underscores the importance of the PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) principle in energy management. The planning stage can be significantly enhanced by using SanFlex-DST, which offers a clear picture of current energy flows and points out areas for improvement. By illustrating energy consumption trends and possible savings, this application can help energy managers throughout the planning stage and support informed decision-making and continual improvement.

The summary of the critical results is represented as follows:

- The tool allows users to update constant factors like cost, carbon footprint, energy storage efficiency, maximum renewable energy generation, and refresh graphs by updating energy flow values and adjusting sliders. It relies on data collection and value manipulation, requiring industry experts to deliver accurate information.
- The result showed a decrease in overall CO₂ emissions from 387.2 t CO₂/year before the adoption of efficient technology in scenario 1 to 329.9 t CO₂/year after including RE and heat recovery in scenario 2. Energy storage systems in scenario 3 resulted in a CO₂ emission decrease of 308.7 t CO₂/year. Scenario 4 showed that implementing all suggested technologies resulted in the most significant reduction in carbon footprint by 27%–279.7 t CO₂/year.

- In terms of energy cost, by including RE and recoverable heat solutions in scenario 2, the overall energy cost decreased from €373 million to €324.3 million. In scenario 3, energy storage options led to a €307.9 million energy cost. Scenario 4 saw the most substantial decrease in energy prices when all suggested solutions were put into effect. The total energy cost dropped by 26 % to €274.7 million following the incorporation of RE, energy storage, and heat recovery systems.
- In conclusion, the findings and conclusions of the current study will be of assistance to practitioners working in the industrial sector regarding the enhancement of efficiency and the promotion of the sustainability of industries.

Future works

There are numerous other variables when analyzing energy management in industries. Since the tool was designed for a FLEX4FACT project, operational and maintenance cost calculations were not included in this study for the present version. The authors are aware of the tool's potential for improvement, and in future versions of the tool, developers will explore operational and maintenance costs as examples of how to incorporate more considerations into final cost estimations.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Arman Ashabi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mohamed Mostafa:** Data curation. **Andriy Hryshchenko:** Supervision. **Ken Bruton:** Supervision. **T.J. O’Sullivan Dominic:** Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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